

IMPORTANT SCIENTIFIC FEATURES OF ORAL TRANSLATION

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Abstract. *The aim of this thesis is to demonstrate the attributes of translation of journalistic materials in socio-political settings provided via examples in English and Uzbek languages. The analysis of translation of socio-political terms showed that the translator should pay attention to the translation of abbreviations, attributive expressions, stylistic expressive means and devices, socio-political terminology, phraseology, informal vocabulary.*

Keywords: *discourse, publication, social, political, media, original context, linguistic, public.*

Journalism is meant to place the public good above all else and uses specific methods to gather and assess information [5]. Journalism plays a crucial role in informing the public and shaping societal discourse. This introduction outlines the significance of journalism in society and introduces the central theme of the thesis: the translation of socio-political journalism from English to Uzbek. It highlights the challenges posed by linguistic and cultural differences and sets the stage for exploring effective translation strategies.

Central to this proposal is the investigation of the complex handle of interpreting socio-political news coverage from English to Uzbek, exploring the imposing etymological and social boundaries in that. By laying uncovered the challenges characteristic in this endeavor, this presentation sets the arrange for a comprehensive investigation of successful interpretation procedures pointed at bridging linguistic and social chasms.

2. Delving into the intricacies of sociolinguistics, the nuanced factors influencing language borrowing trends within the Uzbek linguistic landscape, with a keen focus on socio-political discourse. The process of lexical borrowing is caused by a whole complex of reasons, in which linguistic, psychological, social, logical, etc. reasons are intertwined [2]. It meticulously scrutinizes the profound impact of globalization and cultural exchange on lexical enrichment, unraveling the complex tapestry of linguistic evolution. Furthermore, it probes the labyrinthine realm of translating political terminology and concepts between English and Uzbek, shedding light on the myriad challenges inherent in this process.

The acquisition of lexical units from different languages serves to enrich the lexicology of the Uzbek language at the expense of terms, expressions, idioms and neologisms. New expressions and terms are updated in the wide diversity of fields and socio-political sphere is not exception in this sense [2]. Lexical units are related to our social and political life and linguistic dictionary is getting rich and diverse. The sociolinguistic flow fundamental language borrowing patterns in Uzbek, especially inside socio-political talk, are altogether inspected. The impact of globalization, mechanical progressions, and universal political, financial, and social trades on lexical enhancement is analyzed. Besides, the interaction between internal (linguistic) and external (social) components in forming dialect advancement inside the socio-political environment is investigated in profundity. By diving into the multifaceted reasons for lexical borrowing, counting etymological, mental, social, and consistent variables, this segment gives a comprehensive understanding of the complexities included in language evolution.

Interpretation of Political terminology and concepts [1]. The complexities of translating political phrasing and concepts from English to Uzbek. It addresses the challenges postured by contrasts in linguistic structures and social foundations between the two languages. By looking at particular examples of political terms and their interpretations, the section highlights the require for inventive interpretation procedures to precisely pass on nuanced implications. Additionally, the significance of keeping up social sensitivity and consistency to the initial setting in political elucidations is underscored, emphasizing the portion of translators as go between dialects and societies. Drawing on sociolinguistic theories and language borrowing trends, the sociopolitical factors influence lexical borrowings and linguistic transformations in the Uzbek language. The analysis explores the impact of international communication on language evolution and highlights the complexities of translating socio-political terms and concepts between English and Uzbek.

Through a comprehensive review of translation techniques, including transliteration, transcription, borrowing, and transformation strategies employed by translators to navigate linguistic and cultural barriers. It discusses the importance of adaptation and cultural sensitivity in ensuring the accuracy and accessibility of translated texts.

Following words can be considered as good examples of new words borrowed from English to Uzbek in social and political spheres.

Social: Selfi (selfie), Stiker (sticker), Emodji (emoji), Dizayn (design), Trend (trend), Kontent (content), Sotsial tarmoq (social network), Sosial media (social media), Koment (comment), Like (like), Follou (follow), Share (share), Vlog (blog), Bloger (blogger), Video-blog (vlog), Aplikatsiya (application), Veb-sayt (website), Geymifikatsiya (gamification), Trafik (traffic), Abonent (subscriber), Abonenti (subscribers), Hashteg (hashtag), Vayral (viral), Influenser (influencer), Endorsment (endorsement), Sotsial markaz (social hub), Profil (profile), Doycha (douche), Geym (game), Kvest (quest), Akkaunt (account), Pleylist (playlist), Chat (chat).

Political: Demokratiya (democracy), Republika (republic), Partiya (party), Prezident (president), Konstitutsiya (constitution), Kandidat (candidate), Eleksiyalar (elections), Oppozitsiya (opposition), Parlament (parliament), Senator (senator), Gubernator (governor), Diplomatiya (diplomacy), Referendum (referendum), Konfederatsiya (confederation), Prokuror (prosecutor), Bosh sekretar (press secretary).

4. Results:

By examining the role of media as an intermediary in shaping public perceptions of socio-political events, the influence of journalistic narratives on audience interpretation. It analyzes how translation choices can impact the portrayal of international conflicts and political developments, emphasizing the need for linguistic and cultural fidelity in journalistic translations. In the contemporary media landscape, journalists serve as gatekeepers of information, curating and disseminating narratives that frame our understanding of global affairs. Through the selection of stories, the framing of issues, and the language used to convey information, media outlets wield considerable influence in shaping public discourse and shaping collective attitudes towards socio-political events. Central to this process is the role of translation in bridging linguistic and cultural divides. As news stories traverse national borders and linguistic boundaries, they undergo a process of translation that can significantly impact their interpretation and reception by audiences. Translation choices, ranging from lexical selection to syntactical structure, can shape the tone, emphasis, and underlying implications of journalistic narratives. In the context of international conflicts and political developments, the stakes are particularly high, as translation can either

facilitate mutual understanding or perpetuate misconceptions and biases. The nuances of language and cultural context can profoundly shape how events are portrayed, with subtle differences in translation choices carrying the potential to influence public perceptions and policy decisions. Emphasizing the need for linguistic and cultural fidelity in journalistic translations, this analysis underscores the ethical imperative of accuracy and impartiality in media representation. Translators and journalists alike bear a responsibility to faithfully convey the nuances of meaning and context inherent in the source material, avoiding distortions or omissions that may skew audience interpretation. Moreover, the role of media as a conduit for cross-cultural communication underscores the importance of linguistic diversity and intercultural competence in the journalistic profession. Another challenge lies in accurately translating cultural references and nuances specific to English-speaking societies into Uzbek. This requires a thorough understanding of both cultures and backgrounds in order to convey the intended meaning effectively. Expressing complex and abstract ideas found in socio-political news can be particularly challenging [4]. By embracing linguistic pluralism and prioritizing cultural sensitivity, media practitioners can contribute to a more nuanced and inclusive understanding of global events, fostering empathy, dialogue, and cooperation across borders. The influence of journalistic narratives on audience interpretation underscores the pivotal role of media in shaping public perceptions of socio-political events. By recognizing the significance of translation choices in mediating cross-cultural communication, media practitioners can uphold principles of accuracy and integrity, fostering a more informed and nuanced understanding of international conflicts and political developments.

5. Discussion:

Exploring the integration of foreign words and the development of synonyms in the Uzbek language, this section contextualizes translation challenges within the broader framework of globalization and cultural exchange. It discusses the implications of linguistic transformation for socio-political discourse and underscores the importance of adaptation in facilitating cross-cultural communication. Exploring the integration of foreign words and the development of synonyms in the Uzbek language offers profound insights into the dynamic nature of language evolution, particularly within the context of globalization and cultural exchange. This process not only sheds light on the translation challenges encountered but also highlights the intricate interplay between linguistic transformation and socio-political discourse.

In the realm of globalization, where cultural boundaries blur and interactions become increasingly interconnected, languages naturally absorb words and concepts from other cultures. This influx of foreign vocabulary into Uzbek poses both challenges and opportunities for translators and language enthusiasts alike. On one hand, the infusion of foreign words enriches the lexicon, offering new nuances and shades of meaning. On the other hand, it necessitates careful consideration of how these borrowed terms align with the linguistic structure and cultural ethos of Uzbek [3].

Synonymous to the integration of foreign words is the development of synonyms within the Uzbek language itself. As language evolves, new expressions and variations emerge to convey similar concepts or ideas. This phenomenon not only reflects the creative nature of language users but also underscores the adaptability of Uzbek in accommodating diverse linguistic expressions.

Within the broader framework of globalization and cultural exchange, the implications of linguistic transformation extend far beyond mere semantics. Language serves as a powerful medium for conveying values, beliefs, and ideologies, shaping socio-political discourse in

profound ways. As foreign words permeate the Uzbek vocabulary, they carry with them cultural connotations and worldviews that influence how ideas are communicated and perceived.

6. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this thesis highlights the significance of translation techniques in bridging linguistic and cultural divides in socio-political journalism. It emphasizes the role of translators as mediators of information and advocates for strategic adaptation to ensure the accuracy and cultural appropriateness of translated texts. By overcoming linguistic and cultural barriers, translators can enhance the accessibility and effectiveness of socio-political journalism in the Uzbek-speaking context.

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